

A FIVE-STAGE KOREAN IDIOMS TEACHING AND LEARNING MODEL FOR FLUENCY IN USAGE

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Abstract. *This paper proposes a five-stage Korean idiom teaching and learning model designed to achieve fluency in idiom usage. The model caters to learners of all levels, with activities and idiom difficulty adjusted accordingly. The core concept is to move learners beyond simply understanding idioms to actively incorporating them into communication. Playful activities are emphasized for beginners, while higher levels delve into the cultural background and origin of idioms.*

Keywords: *korean idiom, idiom education, learning model, fluency, communication.*

INTRODUCTION:

The Korean idiom teaching and learning model to achieve the goal of Korean idiom education is designed in 5 stages by introducing Bernard [1]. We would like to present it by applying the introduction preparation stage - presentation stage - practice stage - actual use stage - confirmation and inspection stage.

Korean idiom teaching and learning model

Provide information	Introduction preparation stage	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Motivation · Guess what you learn
	Presentation stage	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Awareness of learning content · Present idioms
Understand and apply	Practice steps	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Beginner: Play-centered learning · Intermediate: Expression learning · Advanced: Inquiry learning
	Actual usage steps	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Expressions compared to idioms in one's own country · Expressions linked to real life
Knowledge check/ assessment	Verification and inspection steps	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Check what you have learned · Present learning-related tasks

It is desirable that each class stage is not conducted independently, but is organically connected to each other. The same Korean idiom teaching and learning model is applied at the elementary, intermediate, and advanced levels. At the beginner level, the learning is mainly focused on understanding idioms through play-centered learning, and at the intermediate level, based on basic knowledge of idioms. The emphasis is on learning expressions, and at the advanced

level, the origin of idioms and the lifestyles of Koreans through idioms should be understood, and a model in which learners explore and solve problems on their own should be applied.

The purpose of Korean idiom education is to enable learners to clearly understand the intent of others' expressions and to clearly convey their thoughts to others. However, if Korean idiom education only focuses on understanding Korean idioms, smooth communication will not be possible and it will be difficult to achieve the educational purpose. Therefore, as suggested in the educational goals, education of Korean idioms should focus on accurately understanding the meaning of Korean idioms and using them effectively to be able to use Korean idioms fluently.

For beginner learners, we provide idioms with every day, easy-to-use constituent vocabulary and with high semantic transparency, while for advanced learners, we provide idioms with difficult constituent vocabulary. It is necessary to classify and teach idioms whose meaning is unclear, requiring background knowledge such as history and culture, by grade.

In the beginner level, foreign learners lack context and situational awareness, as this is the basic stage in vocabulary education, and lack understanding of history or cultural background knowledge. Therefore, the constituent vocabulary selected in Chapter 3 has easy meaning, is frequently used by Koreans, and has high meaning. It is relatively transparent, so it is easy to associate the meaning of the idiom, and it is a desirable step to prioritize teaching idioms that are similar to the cultural background of foreign learners.

Class stage teaching		Learning activities	Class materials
Provide information	Introduction preparation stage	1) Present idioms to learn and learning goals 2) Activating required learning tasks and learners' background knowledge 3) Motivating learners to learn idioms 4) Encourage awareness of the importance of idioms	PPT
	Presentation stage	1) Infer the meaning of learning idioms using audio-visual materials 2) Explanation of meaning of learning idioms, comparison with learner's native language 3) Presenting the meaning and use of learning idiom situation examples	Pictures, photos, objects, cartoons, videos, etc.
Understand and apply	Practice stage	1) Check the guessed meaning 2) Create an idiom dictionary (notebook) 3) Role-play with idioms 4) Complete sentences with idioms that fit the situation 5) Find idioms after listening to explanations ※ Present context, convey meaning, complete dialogue, etc.	Idiom dictionary, usage sheet

	Actual usage steps	1) Create situations to express learned idioms 2) Creating conversations using learned idioms, etc.	
Evaluation/Confirmation	Confirmation and inspection steps	1) Organize and confirm what you have learned 2) Writing homework, etc.	Application paper, manuscript paper

At the beginner level, Korean idiom education involves learning Korean idioms through the introduction preparation stage - presentation stage - practice stage - actual use stage - confirmation and inspection stage. In the introduction preparation stage, the learner is motivated, specific learning goals are presented, and It is most important to ensure that learners clearly understand what they are studying.

This is because Koreans use idioms unconsciously, but for foreign learners, they are special expressions that express a third meaning that cannot be understood through vocabulary alone. In the presentation stage, pictures, photos, objects, cartoons, videos, etc. are presented to learners. It is important to arouse interest in idiom education. In addition, using fairy tales that unfold as short stories can be an effective method as it can prevent learning from being boring. Simple example sentences are presented so that the meaning and use can be easily understood. In the practice stage, it is a process of checking whether the idioms explained above have been properly understood. Since beginner learners still lack grammar or vocabulary skills, the focus is on play such as flipping idiom cards, finding idioms by looking at pictures (cartoons), idiom crossword puzzles, playing idiom bingo, and creating idiom sentences. In the actual use stage, students learn to use the learned idioms and apply them to various situations. In other words, it is a step to perform a task by combining idioms with other linguistic elements, and it is important to be able to speak using idioms in simple speaking situations. In the practical application stage, you learn to use the learned idioms and apply them to various situations. In other words, it is a stage in which idioms are combined with other linguistic elements to perform tasks, and it is important to be able to speak using idioms in simple speaking situations. The confirmation and inspection stage is a stage in which the learned content is organized and confirmed. Beginner Considering the learners' vocabulary use ability, we present easy tasks so as not to burden the learners, so that they can complete them on their own through self-evaluation.

REFERENCES

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